

Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and Copper(II) with 1-Guanyl-5-Methyl Pyrazole-3-Carboxylic Acid as Primary Ligand and Heterocyclic Amines as Co-ligands

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Several mixed ligand complexes of the type $M(\text{GMPC})\cdot B$ [$\text{GMPC} = 1\text{-guanyl-5-methyl pyrazole-3-carboxylic acid}$; $M = \text{Co(II), Ni(II) or Cu(II)}$; $B = \text{H}_2\text{O, NH}_3, \text{py, pico, bipy or } o\text{-phen}$] have been synthesised and physico-chemically characterised. Magnetic and electronic spectral features classify all the Co(II) and Cu(II) species as distorted octahedral ones while the mixed Ni(II) complexes have been characterised as planar or octahedral or even as a mixture of both the forms depending on the nature of coligand. IR spectra indicate the pyrazole nitrogen, the carboxyl oxygen and the nitrogen of the guanyl component as potential binding sites in the primary ligand. Derivatographic studies reveal, in general, the thermal stability of the complex species, giving an indication of the mode of cleavage of the molecules at increasing temperatures.

AS a part of our comprehensive programme^{1,2} on the synthesis and structural characterisation of the metal complexes of pyrazole-based ligands, we recently reported the coordination behaviour of a new pyrazole-based tridentate ligand (ONN) by characterisation of its mixed ligand complexes with nickel(II)³ and cobalt(II)⁴. The present investigation reports the synthesis of the mixed ligand complexes of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) with 1-guanyl-5-methyl pyrazole-3-carboxylic acid ($\text{GMPC} = \text{I}$), a potential (ONN) tridentate as primary ligand and heterocyclic amines as coligands, and their structural characterisation from magnetic, spectral (electronic and vibrational) and derivatographic studies.

Experimental

All chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The solvents were purified and dried in the usual manner before use.

Preparation of the ligand ($\text{GMPC} = \text{I}$): 1-Guanyl-5-methyl pyrazole-3-carboxylic acid ($\text{GMPC} = \text{I}$) as its monohydrochloride was prepared by a condensation reaction between the sodium salt of ethylaceto-pyruvate and aminoguanidine hydrochloride⁵ following a method very similar to that adopted by Knorr *et al*⁶. The product, on recrystallisation from

hot water, produced a white crystalline compound, m.p. 215°. (Found: C, 35.10; H, 4.38; N, 27.26. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_9\text{N}_4\text{O}_2\text{Cl}$ requires C, 35.20; H, 4.40; N, 27.38%).

Preparation of the metal complexes:

(a) $M(\text{GMPC})\cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($M = \text{Ni, Cu}$): Ethanolic solution of hydrated metal(II) acetate (0.005 mole) was mixed with an aqueous solution of the ligand (0.005 mole). The desired copper(II) species separated out immediately on stirring as deep green crystals. To isolate the nickel(II) compound as light blue crystals, the resulting solution had to be adjusted to $\text{pH} \approx 6$ with dilute ammonia and left overnight. In each case, the compound was filtered, washed with water and alcohol and finally dried over fused CaCl_2 .

(b) $M(\text{GMPC})\cdot B\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($M = \text{Co, Cu}$; $B = \text{py, picolines}$): To the solution obtained by mixing an ethanolic solution of the hydrated metal(II) acetate (0.005 mole) and an aqueous solution of the ligand (0.005 mole), was added the respective base in excess to have a pH around 5-6. The mixture was kept at water-bath temperature for 15-20 min and the precipitated compound was collected as above after a final washing with acetone.

(c) $M(\text{GMPC})\cdot \text{NH}_3$ ($M = \text{Ni, Cu}$): The preparative method as outlined for (a) above was followed except that the ammonia solution was added in excess ($\text{pH} \approx 8-9$) to isolate the desired ammonia adducts.

(d) $\text{Ni}(\text{GMPC})\cdot B\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($B = \text{py, picolines, bipy, } o\text{-phen}$) and $\text{Cu}(\text{GMPC})\cdot B\cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($B = \text{bipy, } o\text{-phen}$): Ethanolic solution of hydrated metal(II) acetate (0.005 mole) was mixed with an aqueous solution of

the ligand (0.005 mole). The respective base (slight excess over 0.005 mole) was added to the resulting solution followed by the addition of ammonia solution to have a pH around 6-7. The desired micro-crystalline base adduct separated out on concentrating at water-bath temperature and was collected as above.

Elemental analyses and physical measurements: Nitrogen, carbon, hydrogen and metal contents of the complexes were determined by standard literature⁷ procedures. The physico-chemical measurements like magnetic susceptibilities, diffuse reflectance spectra, vibrational spectra and derivatographic analyses on the solid samples were carried out as described earlier⁴.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data supporting the proposed formulations of the complex species along with some of their pertinent physico-chemical properties are given in Table 1. All the mixed ligand complexes are insoluble in water and even in inert and donor organic solvents.

The room temperature magnetic moment values (4.9-5.1 B.M.) of the present cobalt(II) complexes are significantly higher than the reported⁸ spin-only value (3.89 B.M.). The higher values might result from the high orbital contribution originating from the intrinsic orbital angular momentum in the octahedral ground state⁹. A small but perceptible increase in the μ_B values of the complexes in the order of the coligated base $\text{py} < \beta\text{-pico} < \gamma\text{-pico}$ may be reconciled in terms of increasing basicity as well as increasing donor properties of these coligands in the same order^{10,11}. The diffuse reflectance spectra of the complexes show two main bands located at 9000 and 20,000 cm^{-1} which, as first approximation, are attributable to spin allowed transitions, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F) (\nu_1)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P) (\nu_3)$, respectively in an average field of octahedral (O_h) symmetry. The splitting of the ν_3 band into two of more components (appearing as shoulders or very weak bands) may be due to the presence of low symmetry (approximating to C_2) components in the ligand field¹². The calculated¹³ values of the parameters, D_q (974-1013 cm^{-1}) and B (795-809 cm^{-1}) are consistent with an average octahedral environ-

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MAGNETIC AND REFLECTANCE SPECTRAL DATA FOR THE COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour	Analysis % ; Found (Calcd.)				μ_{eff} B.M. (303K)
		N	M	C	H	
Co(GMPC).py.2H ₂ O	Deep pink	20.51 (20.59)	17.40 (17.36)	39.82 (38.82)	4.44 (4.41)	4.90
Co(GMPC) β -pico.2H ₂ O	Light pink	19.80 (19.77)	16.65 (16.66)	42.01 (40.67)	4.78 (4.80)	4.95
Co(GMPC) γ -pico.2H ₂ O	Light pink	19.78 (19.77)	16.62 (16.66)	41.30 (40.67)	5.05 (4.80)	5.08
Ni(GMPC).3H ₂ O	Light blue	20.14 (20.19)	21.12 (21.06)	26.02 (25.80)	4.88 (4.30)	3.28
Ni(GMPC).NH ₃	Deep red	22.16 (23.96)	24.58 (24.29)	29.60 (29.77)	4.04 (3.72)	Diamagnetic
Ni(GMPC).py	Red	23.10 (23.05)	19.30 (19.33)	—	—	Diamagnetic
Ni(GMPC) α -pico	Light red	21.98 (22.08)	18.56 (18.52)	45.90 (45.32)	4.26 (4.09)	2.10
Ni(GMPC) β -pico	Deep red	22.03 (22.08)	18.49 (18.52)	46.00 (45.32)	4.15 (4.09)	Diamagnetic
Ni(GMPC) γ -pico.H ₂ O	Deep red	20.98 (20.89)	17.32 (17.49)	—	—	Diamagnetic
Ni(GMPC).bipy.4H ₂ O	Light blue	18.60 (18.56)	12.96 (12.96)	41.98 (42.41)	3.89 (3.97)	3.04
Ni(GMPC).o-phen.5H ₂ O	Light violet	16.75 (16.98)	11.82 (11.87)	—	—	2.95
Cu(GMPC).3H ₂ O	Dirty green	19.80 (19.76)	22.00 (22.41)	25.42 (25.39)	4.52 (4.23)	1.92
Cu(GMPC).NH ₃ .3H ₂ O	Brown	23.32 (23.30)	21.04 (21.13)	—	—	1.91
Cu(GMPC).py.2H ₂ O	Brown	20.25 (20.32)	18.63 (18.44)	39.45 (38.31)	4.40 (4.35)	1.93
Cu(GMPC) α -pico.2H ₂ O	Brown	19.38 (19.53)	17.69 (17.71)	—	—	2.01
Cu(GMPC) β -pico.3H ₂ O	Greenish brown	18.50 (18.59)	16.81 (16.87)	—	—	1.98
Cu(GMPC) γ -pico.2H ₂ O	Greenish brown	19.48 (19.53)	17.65 (17.71)	39.03 (40.16)	5.01 (4.74)	2.04
Cu(GMPC).bipy.2H ₂ O	Dirty green	19.81 (19.83)	15.20 (15.07)	44.99 (45.45)	4.32 (4.27)	2.01
Cu(GMPC).o-phen.H ₂ O	Deep green	19.74 (19.65)	14.59 (14.86)	—	—	2.15

ment around the central metal ion¹⁴. The calculated band position for using the relationship $\nu_2 = \nu_1 + 10D_4$ suggests the shoulder around 19000 cm⁻¹ in Co(GMPC). β -pico.2H₂O to be the ν_2 transition.

The nickel(II) complexes, Ni(GMPC).B.nH₂O (B=H₂O, bipy, *o*-phen), show magnetic moment values (2.90-3.30 B.M.) quite typical of six-coordinate spin-free octahedral species. The reflectance spectra of these mixed complexes exhibit bands in the region of 10,600-11,000 and 16,600-18,000 cm⁻¹ assignable to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1) and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_2) transitions, respectively in O_h symmetry¹⁵. The additional band around 22,000 cm⁻¹ may be caused by spin-forbidden transition ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}(D)$ ¹⁶. The ν_2/ν_1 values (ca 1.55-1.66) also support their octahedral geometry and suggest a strong configuration interaction between the high-spin T_{1g}(P) and T_{1g}(F) excited states¹⁷.

The red nickel(II) complexes, Ni(GMPC).B.nH₂O (B=NH₃, py, β -pico, γ -pico), are diamagnetic and possess a single ground term ${}^1A_{1g}$. The electronic spectra of these complexes are characterised by a broad ligand field band in the region of 18,000-20,000 cm⁻¹ suggesting their square planar geometry. The broadness of the band represents a group of two to three transitions ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{2g}$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_g$ under a square planar environment around the central metal ion^{18,19}.

The markedly subnormal magnetic moment value of 2.10 B.M. for Ni(GMPC) α -pico as compared to those expected for spin-free octahedral Ni(II) complexes along with the appearance of d.r.s. bands near 9000, 17,500 and 23,000 cm⁻¹ followed by a shoulder around 13,000 cm⁻¹ are suggestive of the coexistence of both paramagnetic octahedral (arising from association between the planar monomers) and diamagnetic square forms in the same complex species in the solid state^{20,21}. This anomalous magnetic moment might also result from the thermal population of low-lying triplet state of nickel(II) resulting in the magnetic cross over between the singlet and the triplet ground states²².

The room temperature magnetic moment values of 1.90-2.20 B.M. for the present copper(II) complexes are well in accord with those having distorted octahedral configuration²³. The reflectance spectra of the species show in general a broad asymmetric band appearing in the region 15,150-17,000 cm⁻¹. For octahedral copper(II) complexes, three transitions from the ground state viz., ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$ (ν_1), ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ (ν_2) and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ (ν_3) are expected; all these transitions being very close in energy, often only one broad band envelope appears. The width and asymmetry of the present spectral bands suggest a distorted octahedral configuration [in the Cu(II) species] with a symmetry lower than O_h due to the presence of mixed-ligand field around the central copper(II) ion²⁴.

The extreme insolubility of all the present mixed-ligand complexes in water and common organic solvents indicates their polymeric nature. This poly-

merisation might result from intermolecular bridging through the secondary donor sites (present in the guanyl group and/or carboxyl group) of the primary ligand molecule (see ir spectra).

Infrared spectra : Infrared spectral data for the present mixed-ligand complexes are somewhat complicated because of the vibrations of the pyrazole ring (of the primary ligand) and coligands like py, pico, bipy and *o*-phen present in the same complex species. However, careful comparison of the characteristic band frequencies of the primary ligand, GMPCH₂.HCl, with those of its metal complexes gives positive information regarding the bonding sites. The ir bands at 3560 and 3420 cm⁻¹ assignable to hydrogen bonded $\nu(N-H)$ and $\nu(O-H)$ of the free ligand molecule undergo shift to lower frequency side on complexation, indicating the rupture of the hydrogen bonds and its participation in coordination. The $\nu_{as}(N-H)$ and $\nu_s(N-H)$ of the ligand appearing around 3380-3280 and 3150 cm⁻¹, respectively disappear with the appearance of a new broad band around 3350-3000 cm⁻¹ (the broadening of the bands may be due to the inter or intramolecular interaction) in the metal complexes, thereby suggesting deprotonation of one of the N-H groups of the guanyl group (-C=NH) on complexation forming an M-N

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NH₂

bond²⁵. The band at 1690 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand attributable to $\nu_{as}(COO^-)$ vibration shows a negative shift (around 1670-1630 cm⁻¹) clearly demonstrating the involvement of the carboxyl group in coordination²⁶. The mixed-complexes show the characteristic band frequencies for the secondary coligands (py, pico, bipy, phen, etc.) which agree well with those reported earlier showing their coordinated nature in the corresponding adducts^{27,28}. (These coligands are coordinated as the metal ion through their tertiary nitrogen atoms). The additional ir band around 1000-900 cm⁻¹ in all the hydrated complexes except the γ -pico adduct of Ni(II) is due to the rocking mode of coordinated water²⁹. The far ir spectrum of Ni(GMPC).3H₂O (containing no N-heterocyclic coligand) shows a distinct band around 320 cm⁻¹ which can be clearly assigned to M-N (ring) stretching vibration³⁰ providing evidence of the fact that the pyrazolyl-tertiary nitrogen is bonded to the metal ion. The additional ir band appearing at 495 cm⁻¹(s) can safely be assigned to M-N (guanyl residue) vibration³¹⁻³³ thus giving a positive indication of the coordination of guanyl nitrogen (-C=NH) in complexation.

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This conclusion is in agreement with the X-ray crystallographic studies on several pyrazole-metal complexes^{34,35}. The ir spectral studies, thus, infer that 1-guanyl-5-methyl pyrazole-3-carboxylic acid (GMPCH₂) behaves as a doubly negatively charged tridentate having ONN donor set in forming the mixed-ligand complexes with Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) coligated with heterocyclic amines. The following structural representation can be made for

the present planar (A) and octahedral species (B and C).

Derivatographic analysis :

The results of DTG, DTA and TG analyses on some of the representative mixed-species are very much similar to our earlier reports^{3,4}. The derivatograms of the complex species correspond in a stepwise manner with the loss of water (both coordinated and lattice water molecules at different temperature) and the heterocyclic amines (coligands) followed by simultaneous decarboxylation and loss of the guanyl group within the temperature range 300-350° to form an intermediate oxo-mono complex, $[MO(mp)]_n$ (mp=methylpyrazole), as suggested earlier³ (formed via the formation of an oxo-bis complex, $[MO(mp)_2]_n$). Except the anhydrous species none of the intermediates could be isolated because of their brief existence at such high temperatures. The final decomposition of the complexes takes place above 400° resulting in the formation of corresponding metal oxide. The mechanism of the suggested thermal reactions agrees well with that reported earlier³.

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